

MORE ON THE SMALLEST CRAB SPIDERS IN AFRICA (ARANEAE: THOMISIDAE: PARABOMIS)

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Abstract

The frog spiders of the genus *Parabomis* are the smallest crab spiders known from Africa. In this paper we report on the colour of live specimens of three species, *P. martini*, *P. pilosus* and *P. megae*. Notes are provided on the general behaviour of *P. megae* from Zimbabwe.

Keywords: Africa, plant-dwellers, Bominæ

INTRODUCTION

In a recent publication by Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2020), the crab spiders of the genus *Parabomis* Kulczyński, 1901 from Africa were revised for the first time. They are very small, only 3 mm in body length, and are the smallest crab spiders known (Fig. 1). With their round bodies, they resemble a seed pot.

Parabomis shares with the other Bominæ the globular body shape, small size and very short legs without spines. They share with *Thomisops* and *Holopelus* the peg-like setae on the promargins of the chelicerae. They can be distinguished by their high carapace, the very broad sloping clypeus, as well as the eyes that are grouped far apart (Fig. 2). *Parabomis* male palps have both a ventral apophysis and a strongly developed retrolateral apophysis on the tibia.

Six *Parabomis* species are presently known from Africa:

- *P. elsae* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020 (South Africa)
- *P. levanderi* Kulczyński, 1901 (Eritrea)
- *P. martini* Lessert, 1919 (Tanzania and rest of Africa)
- *P. megae* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020 (Zimbabwe)
- *P. pilosus* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020 (Botswana)
- *P. wandae* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020 (Ghana)

In this paper we report on the colour of live specimens, with notes on their general behaviour. All specimens housed in collections are alcohol-preserved material, and only on receiving photographs of living specimens did we realize that they lose their colour in alcohol. The second author observed and photographed females and a male *Parabomis* from Zimbabwe. He was also able to capture some of their interesting behavior on camera.

METHODS

As part of the SANSa Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012) photographs were obtained of live specimens. It became clear that the live specimens differ in colour from specimens preserved in alcohol. Images of three species, *P. martini*, *P. pilosus* and *P. megae* became available for comparison.

The second author observed and photographed several individuals of *P. megae* in a garden in Zimbabwe. He was able to capture some of their interesting behaviour on video, shared online at <https://youtu.be/ArCrB0tE1PY>. These are the first observations of their behaviour.

RESULTS

All members of *Parabomis* are small spiders (males 1.9 mm, females 3 mm). In Fig. 1 their size is compared to the tip of a match. In adult females, the extended abdomen can almost resemble a round seed pot (Figs 2 & 3). When they rest on the vegetation they resemble small frogs with the shape of the carapace and abdomen, and the short legs that fold around the body.

FIGURES 1–4. *Parabomis* sp. (1) Indicating the small size; (2–3) Female with extended abdomen; (4) Live specimen resemble a frog.

Due to their small size they are not easily seen. According to label data of specimens in collections, they have been mainly collected beating trees and sweeping grass and herbs in the Grassland (Haddad *et al.* 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.* 2011) and Thicket Biomes. They have been collected from a variety of habitats ranging from thorny bushveld to the undergrowth of coastal dune forest.

At Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve they have been sampled from yellow flowering *Vachellia* trees, as well as from grasses during the same survey period. From label data, species have been collected from trees such as *Buddleja saligna*, *Euclea crispa*, *Dombeya rotundifolia*, *Vitex rehmannia*, *Vachellia* spp. and *Pterocelastrus tricuspidatus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2009; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2020). In Namibia, specimens were collected from the tree *Grewia monticola*, and according to Lawrence (1928) the spider closely resembles its flowers.

Colour: It has become clear that the museum specimens used in the revision of *Parabomis* lost their colour in alcohol. From the photographs of living specimens it became clear that they are more colourful when alive. The colour of three species based on life specimens is discussed here.

***Parabomis martini*:** This species has been collected from a variety of habitats in the Grassland and Savanna Biomes, ranging from grass, trees in thorny bushveld, and the undergrowth of coastal dune forest. It is widespread in Africa and has been recorded from Tanzania, Kenya, Namibia, Guinea, Malawi, Rwanda, South Africa, Zambia and Zimbabwe. In alcohol the female's carapace is fawn, with the clypeus and eye region strongly infused with white in females (Fig. 5) and darker brown in males (Fig. 7). In a live female photographed at Thyspunt in the Eastern Cape the clypeus and eye area was infused with green and the abdomen had distinct patches of green (Fig. 6). In the male (Fig. 8) the carapace is dark and the abdomen reddish-brown.

FIGURES 5–8 *Parabomis martini*. (5) Colour of alcohol preserved female; (6) Live female from Thyspunt, showing the body infused with green; (7) Colour of alcohol-preserved male; (8) Live male from Thyspunt. Photo credits of live spiders: L. Wiese.

***Parabomis pilosus*:** This species can be recognized by the carapace and abdomen bearing rows of flat-lying translucent club-shaped setae that are longer and denser than in other species, especially on the carapace declivity. The colour of this species do not differ that much from the preserved specimens although the club-shaped setae are less distinct in alcohol material (Fig. 9). They have been sampled from the Okavango Delta in Botswana as well as in the northern parts of the Limpopo Province in South Africa. Specimens were sampled by sweeping grass and herbs. In Tshipise, a female was sampled from a silk retreat made between leaves (Figs 10–12). Adults were sampled in November and December.

FIGURES 9–12. *Parabomis pilosus*. (9) Colour of alcohol preserved female; (10–12) Live female from Tshipise, showing the body infused with brown. Photo credits of live spiders: J. Wilkinson.

***Parabomis megae*:** These small spiders are commonly found in Zimbabwe. A single male specimen was also now identified from the Kruger National Park, South Africa. In alcohol, the female carapace is fawn, with the eye region infused with white (Fig. 13), and in the male dark brown (Fig. 15). In live specimens, the immature female is whitish but becomes more colourful after she has moulted (Fig. 14). In live male specimens the carapace is almost black (Fig. 16).

FIGURES 13–16. *Parabomis megae*. (13) Colour of alcohol-preserved female; (14) Live female from Zimbabwe; (15) Colour of alcohol-preserved male; (16) Live male. Photo credits of live spiders: Jonathan Whitaker.

FIELD OBSERVATIONS IN ZIMBABWE

FIGURES 17–20. *Parabomis megae*. (17) Female on plant in garden in Harare; (18) Male sampled from garden; (19) Palp of male sampled in garden; (20) Male palp from Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2020). Photo credits of live spiders: J. Whitaker.

Identification: The second author observed the small spider walking around on a plant in a garden in Harare, Zimbabwe on October 2020 (Fig. 17) for the first time. It was identified as a *Parabomis* sp., but it was only after a male was collected (Fig. 18) that we were able to identify it as *P. megae*, a species recently described from Zimbabwe (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2020). Females are more difficult to identify and it is mainly the shape of the retrolateral apophysis in the male that helps with identification (Figs 19-20). In *P. megae*, the retrolateral apophysis curves upwards.

Male: The live male has a very dark, almost black carapace, with some of the leg segments dark. It differs from the alcohol-preserved brown males (Fig. 15). In live specimens the carapace, chelicerae, palp and femora are black. The abdomen is white and the dorsal part is covered by a shield-like patch with a mottled reddish-brown colour. These images enabled us to identify a male photographed in the Kruger National Park by Ronelle as *P. megae* (Figs 23-24). *Parabomis megae* was previously only known from Zimbabwe.

Immature and female: The first spider observed was white with only a few black spots (Fig. 25). Only after the final moult (Fig. 26) did the first colour appear on the abdomen (Figs 27-28). The abdomen is still flat, forming crevices and humps in the young female.

On 14 January 2020 a female was seen with extended abdomen, possibly ready to lay eggs. The abdomen was largely extended, round, with a pinkish tint around the anterior abdominal border. The clypeus had a faint greenish hue (Figs 29-30; 33-34).

FIGURES 21–24. *Parabomis megae*. 21-22. Male from garden in Harare; 23-24. Male photographed in the Kruger National Park. Photos: 21-22 J. Whitaker. 23-24 Ronelle.

FIGURES 25–28. *Parabomis megae*. (25) Immature female; (26) Female after moult; (27-28) Female. Photos: J. Whitaker.

FIGURES 29–30. *Parabomis megae*, adult female. Photos: J. Whitaker.

Behaviour: One female was observed over a 24-hour period, beginning mid-afternoon. She was active throughout the afternoon, remaining stationary overnight and for most of the morning (Figs 31-34). Other individuals were observed out on a strand of silk at night, but this one simply sat under a leaf. With their round bodies and short legs, they are clumsy and she frequently lost her footing, dropping down on a silk thread only to climb back up again. Movement between branches was accomplished by letting out silk into the wind and then using it to bridge gaps of up to 1.5m. The legs are so short that they struggle to directly pull out the silk, instead first dropping down on a line (sometimes repeatedly) to initiate a strand, which could then be taken out further by the wind.

This activity can be viewed at <https://youtu.be/ArCrB0tE1PY> Unfortunately due to their small size, they are easily lost in vegetation.

Parabomis strike range is quite limited. They sit by the best flowers (Fig. 35) and catch prey that landed right in front of them (Fig. 36). They seem to be quite successful and feed on a variety of insects visiting the flowers (Figs 37, 38). The males feed while on the plant (Fig. 38) or they hang from a thread (Figs 39, 40) while feeding. This was also seen being done by *Mystaria* species (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015).

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FIGURES 31–34. *Parabomis megae*. (31-32) Young female moving around on leaf; (33-34) Adult female possibly searching for leaf to make a retreat to deposit the eggs. Photos: J. Whitaker.

FIGURES 35–40. *Parabomis megae*. (35-37) Female catching prey; (38-40) Adult male feeding. Photos: J. Whitaker.